

DIGITAL FUTURE AND DIGITAL INHERITANCE

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When a case appears before the court concerning the wills, the judges must find answers to the two following questions:

1. Whether an heir intends to succeed a will or not;
2. If an heir wants to succeed, then, based on which terms.

The succession of wills must be valid, written, signed and witnessed by more than one individual.¹ Traditionally, the inheritance process requires strict rules, which must be established in compliance with the law. But, the criticisms against these strict rules by scholars and professors forced them to change. In 1970, Professor John H. Langbein stated that formalities were needless to clarify a testator indeed wanted to succeed in his inheritance, it mostly represented the purpose of Wills Act formalities.² After a long period of time, the courts began analyzing the cases regulating to succeed the wills thoroughly than whether it complied with Wills Act of formalities or not.³ Currently, almost all states require wills in a written format, a tangible document except for an electronic will.

The necessity for applying the electronic wills unlikely will be increased in the upcoming years. Professors Gerry Beyer and Claire Hargrove clarified the seven barriers which become the reason for decreasing the application of electronic wills:⁴

Technical barriers such as the lack of software that would provide adequate authentication;

Social barriers such as attorneys' reluctance to help create electronic wills;

Economic barriers such as the expense of implementing new technology;

¹ The author is Gökalp Y. Gürer. The title of the article is "No Paper? No Problem: Ushering in Electronic Wills Through California's "Harmless Error" Provision". University of California, Davis, published in 2016.

² Langbein, *supra* note 16, at 489; see also Gürer, *supra* note 18, at 1965–66.

³ *ee*, e.g., *Martina v. Elrod*, 748 S.E.2d 412, 414 (Ga. 2013) ("The doctrine of substantial compliance, though tolerant of 'variations in the mode of expression' utilized to satisfy statutory requisites, nonetheless requires 'actual compliance as to all matters of substance.'" (Quoting *Gen. Elec. Credit Corp. v. Brooks*, 249 S.E.2d 596, 602 (Ga. 1978))); *Smith v. Smith*, 348 S.W.3d 63, 63 (Ky. App. 2011) (holding that the doctrine of substantial compliance could not be used to deem a will compliant where it was signed by only one witness and two were usually required).

⁴ Beyer & Hargrove, *supra* note 26, at 890–96. The title of the article is "Digital Wills: Has the Time Come for Wills to Join the Digital Revolution?". Published on February 2009. The author is Gerry W. Beyer from Texas Tech University.

Motivational barriers such as a lack of recognition of the potential benefits of electronic wills;

Obsolescence barriers stemming from changes in technology, and;

A general resistance to change.

The fast changes in digital world services, cloud services, electronic services, and social networks over the past decades definitely suggest that people become more addicted to using the internet because of its comfort. If we will take into consideration the statistics that 35% of American adults owned a smartphone in 2011, this percentage has nearly doubled up to 68% in 2015.⁵

A comparison of the social networking sites is also useful: In 2007, Twitter had just recently been established⁶, Facebook users number counted nearly 58 million.⁷ Currently, these two big social networks companies' users reached 2 billion users, respectively.⁸

However, it seems that the barriers which are prescribed above by Professors Gerry Beyer and Claire Hargrove – motivational, social, technical, and other barriers are more silent. Despite these facts, people are more reluctant to use them regularly than any other activity in various aspects of their lives.

The practice indicates that the usage of the internet is swiftly increasing despite any interruptions. Simultaneously, the proportion of users will be increasing.

As electronic devices and internet connections are increasing, testators become more inclined to save papers, even vital documents including personal data on such devices or services, and they are likely to expect those documents to have legal effects.

Innovations pushed for or promoted by commercial corporations, such as websites that allow testators to prepare wills inexpensively and simply,⁹ statutes allowing private firms to serve as qualified custodians for electronic wills, services that assist in the creation of verified digital signatures, and

⁵ Monica Anderson, Technology Device Ownership: 2015, PEW RES. CTR. (Oct. 29, 2015),
Online available at: <http://www.pewinternet.org/2015/10/29/technology-device-ownership-2015/>,
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⁶ Twitter was launched on March 21, 2006. Amanda MacArthur, The Real History of Twitter, in Brief, LIFEWIRE (Nov. 7, 2017),
Online available at: <https://www.lifewire.com/history-of-twitter-3288854>, <https://perma.cc/U3RU-M7AW>

⁷ Ami Sedghi, Facebook: 10 Years of Social Networking, in Numbers, THE GUARDIAN: DATABLOG (Feb. 4, 2014, 9:38 AM),
Online available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/news/datablog/2014/feb/04/facebook-in-numbers-statistics>,
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⁸ Kathleen Chaykowski, Mark Zuckerberg: 2 billion Users Means Facebook's "Responsibility Is Expanding," FORBES (June 27, 2017, 1:37 PM), <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kathleenchaykowski/2017/06/27/facebook-officially-hits-2-billion-users>,
<https://perma.cc/GPJ4-EHC8>

⁹ See, e.g., LEGALZOOM, <https://www.legalzoom.com/sem/homepage/>, <https://perma.cc/ZB7H-932E>

electronic notaries imply that the private sector is working to make electronic wills viable.

The only thing that remains to be done to make electronic wills function is for courts and legislators to take a methodical approach to regulate and interpret them. For hundreds of years, there have been no substantial changes in the procedures related to the creation and execution of wills.¹⁰ Courts and legislators must now comprehend the concerns that are likely to arise in the context of electronic wills. As a result, the broad term "electronic will" into the three types of fact patterns that are anticipated to emerge in this field. Offline, online, and qualified custodian electronic wills are susceptible to the generic electronic wills concerns of fraud and obsolescence, but each category has its own set of factors for courts and lawmakers to address. Finally, courts and legislators must decide how to best empower testators' freedom of disposition via their wills — regardless of how they choose to construct them.

Inheritance agreement in a digital age

Civil law is faced with the difficult challenges of a digital age. Some legal problems in Civil Law are not resolved till nowadays and it has to be legally regulated. Nevertheless, the government of Uzbekistan actively participates in the capital market through its SOEs and banks that issue, own, manage various securities, and render intermediary services in the financial market,¹¹ which really helps to develop civil law legislation in some extent.

Inheritance law is a part of Civil law and it also has some legal problems. For example, when inheriting a cryptocurrency or deciding what to do with a social account of the holder after his death. In particular, the new types of legal institutions, such as the inheritance contract impacts digitalization. In this regard, a dilemma concerns how the current regulation and the practice of applying the law must be effectively regulated.

An inheritance contract is assumed as an agreement, the terms of which determine the heir's circle and the procedure for the transfer of rights to the property of the testator after his death.¹² An analysis of the definition and legal norms makes it possible to understand that the main goal of introducing the structure of an inheritance contract is to provide the testator and potential heirs with the opportunity to formally succeed certain rights and obligations

¹⁰ See Caldwell, *supra* note 5, at 467.

¹¹ The authors are Said Gulyamov, Otabek Narziev, Sadoqat Safoeva, Jahongir Juraev. The title of the article is "State Role Securities Market Development in Uzbekistan", published on the American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, on June 18, 2021.

¹² Section V, inheritance law, chapter 66. General provisions on inheritance.

Online available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550>

prescribed in the contract relating to each other. Obviously, the main problem here will be the potential heir's actions in favor of the testator in exchange for guarantees of receiving an inheritance in the near future.

It must be noted that this type of agreement is convenient for making the lifetime maintenance of testators. Because it becomes more effective from the moment when it is signed rather than a will. Also, the inheritance contract is more convenient for older testators, compared with the contract of life maintenance with a dependent, where the real estate ownership rights are not retained by the rent recipient. According to the inheritance contract, the right of ownership (an authority to dispose of) fully remains with the testator.

Nevertheless, there is the problem of establishing the relationship of the inheritance contract with relevant categories. Accordingly, a contract and a will. Unfortunately, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not consider norms establishing the legal force ratio of a will and an inheritance contract. There are significant problems associated with the subject composition, the content, regulation of the inheritance contract, and the consequences of its violation.

Legal researchers of the inheritance law field have analyzed the structure of the inheritance agreement under different legal regimes, which made the unsatisfactory conclusion as "the degree of connection of the testator is so weak and the degree of risk of the heir is so huge which in fact, it makes a will with a clause on compensation for damages in case of cancellation".¹³ It means that how much the inheritance contract is the most beneficial for the testator, the heirs carry the risks as much as possible.

On the other hand, it is criticized due to the lack of protection for the weaker participants in the turnover, especially those who due to their age or health status are at the risk zone of being misled. There is a position that this aspect is not sufficiently taken into account by our legislators in situations where fraudsters take advantage of the excessive gullibility of older people who were unable to adapt to the conditions of a market economy persuading them to make certain transactions.

The hereditary contract establishes excellent conditions only for the elderly. The testator has the right to withdraw from the contract, and can freely dispose of the property but the other party to the contract (or other parties) is responsible

¹³ The title of the article is "International inheritance law - avoiding conflicts of jurisdiction". The authors are Walter Häberling and Alexandra Schnyder. MLL Meyerlustenberger Lachenal Froriep Ltd. Switzerland, published on February 22, 2018.

Online available at: <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=eff04523-1946-42d9-b026-cdd85288e5f1>

for the maintenance of the testator simultaneously. The uniqueness of the inheritance contract under the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is especially evident when compared with similar phenomena in other countries. For example, under German law, the parties are firmly bound by the agreement and the inheritance contract can be terminated only in exceptional cases.¹⁴ Simultaneously, there is a problem of insufficient protection of the future heir. Having assessed all the risks, the heir might refuse to conclude an agreement with the testator. Consequently, there are doubts based on serious arguments that the inheritance contract will often be applied in practice. The potential positive effect of the inheritance agreement for the testator is leveled due to the reluctance to conclude it with potential heirs. It means that the practice of concluding the inheritance contracts and the complete absence of court decision on this matter means that it is too early to discuss about the core meaning of the inheritance contract.

The inheritance contract is effective just in some cases. For instance, it applies to the situation of inheriting the business assets and other property used in entrepreneurship.

An inheritance agreement can be concluded with the aim when the heir begins to develop the use of a digital account (social network account) registered for a commercial purpose. In this case, several economic and legal aspects instantly are resolved: the testator not only introduces the potential heir of the agreement but also transfers the necessary data like keys, passwords, user names, etcetera. Meanwhile, the testator will be able to change the needed data (password, key, etcetera) if he decides to find another heir, but then the heir can sue the testator for losses caused by terminating the contract or not complying with the requirements of the contract. Anyway, there will be economic and legal advantages for all parties of the contract.

The theory and law enforcement practice is now looking for mechanisms improving legislation. However, the practice of entrepreneurship and business activity should find the most effective answer to the application for specific relations of the inheritance contract. The results should be based on the recommendations of citizens and lawyers. Presumably, the legal regulations where the inheritance agreement can solve specific practical problems are entrepreneurship including the inherited rights relating to corporate regulations, as well as, digitalization.

¹⁴ Kroiß, L. *Vorsorge für den Erbfall durch Testament, Erbvertrag und Schenkung* / L. Kroiß. – München. – Bech. – 2019. – 52 s.

Currently, the world is trying to establish the distinctive features of the inherited properties and access of heirs to them, discussing the digitalization process of society and the challenges that the inheritance law faced up with it. Consequently, cryptocurrency and digital rights are increasingly considered in practice as objects of property relations. Therefore, they are subject to inclusion in the estate. The problem of access to such objects will inevitably arise, the exact determination of what exactly the testator owned. These problems can be overcome with the help of a hereditary contract where the parties have the opportunity to determine the list of objects of hereditary succession (including those existing in a digital form), as well as, the procedure for their transfer. Such a mechanism is also beneficial for the testator, who will be sure that his digital objects will pass to the heir.

Thus, the effectiveness of the inheritance contract digitalization can be expressed in two ways. *Firstly*, this is the definition of objects of hereditary succession, the origin, and existence of which may be known to a limited circle of people due to their digital nature: cryptocurrency, social network account or account in the game. In the inheritance contract, such objects will not only be listed but also clearly described. *Secondly*, it is a description of the order of transmission of objects that exist in a "digital" form (for example, the access obtaining order of a "key" to bitcoins). Therefore, the testator can place the key in a safe deposit box with the possibility of accessing it after his death.

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3. Decreto legislativo 10 agosto 2018, n. 101: "Disposizioni per l'adattamento delle disposizioni delle regolamenti (UE) 2016/679 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, del 27 aprile 2016, relative alla protezione dei dati personali con riferimento al trattamento dei dati personali, nonché alla libertà di circolazione di tali dati e che abroga la direttiva 95/46/CE" (regolamento generale sulla protezione dei dati) (GU (Gazzetta ufficiale) Serie Generale n. 205 del 4.9.2018).

4. Authors: Francesco Paolo Patti and Francesca Bartolini. The title of the paper is "Digital inheritance and post mortem data protection: The Italian reform". *European Review of Private Law (ERPL)*, Forthcoming Bocconi Legal Studies Research Paper No. 3397974, 12 pages. Published on 03 June, 2019.
5. Art. 2 terdecies, para 1, Legislative Decree no. 101 of 2018.
6. In recent years, Italian law of succession in recent years has seemed to pay greater attention to the testamentary freedom. See, on the specific issue of disinheritance the comparative overview by F. BARTOLINI & FP PATTI, 'The freedom to disinherit children', *ZEuP (Zeitschrift für Europäisches Privatrecht)* 2018, p 428.
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